

D4.4 ACCORD Solutions Documentation

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Executive Summary

The aim of the ACCORD project is to digitalise the building permitting and compliance procedures to improve the quality and productivity of design and construction processes and support the development of a sustainable built environment. This is achieved by adopting an approach where individual tools are treated as microservices, eliminating the requirement for costly centralised systems that are hard to establish, integrate and manage.

This deliverable presents the technical documentation of all the artefacts developed in *Work Package 4 Solution Development* in the ACCORD project. These key artefacts include:

- A set of ACCORD core services designed to form the core elements of an interoperable digital building permitting system.
- A set of compliance checking microservices that perform the actual work of answering individual decision points within construction regulations.
- API definitions defining how the solutions developed within ACCORD communicate.

The full live technical documentation output of this task has been designed as a webpage. This allows all instructions to be easily navigated and preserved online after the conclusion of the project. This website can be accessed at: [ACCORD Project Documentation](https://docs.accordproject.eu/)¹. The website presents the technical documentation of all the artefacts developed in the ACCORD project.

This document serves as a resource for future developers of digital building permitting solutions, the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry, and the Computing community. It aims to facilitate the practical use and understanding of ACCORD's outputs, which are open-source and adhere to Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles, to maximize reuse and exploitability.

¹ <https://docs.accordproject.eu/>

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the results of the ACCORD project's Task 4.6 Technical Guidelines. This task belongs to Work Package 4 Solutions development. This introduction section first outlines the ACCORD project, states the aims of this document and then summarizes its structure.

1.1 The ACCORD Project

The ACCORD project's objective is to provide a framework for digitalising building permitting and compliance processes using BIM and other data sources, with the end goal of improving the productivity and quality of design and construction processes, supporting the design of climate-neutral buildings and advancing a sustainable built environment in line with the EU Green Deal and New European Bauhaus initiative.

ACCORD is based on the principles that these digitised processes must be human-centred, transparent, and cost-effective for the permit applicants and authorities and, above all, relevant to the industry within which they are to be employed.

To achieve this, ACCORD is developing a Semantic Framework for European digital building permitting processes, regulations, data, and tools. This framework will drive rule formalisation and integration of existing compliance tools as microservices. Solutions and tools are to be developed, providing consistency, interoperability and reliability with national regulatory frameworks, processes, and standards. It will enable the integration of technical solutions for automating compliance checking of buildings in their design, construction, and renovation/demolition lifecycle phases.

To ensure the industry relevance of the project work, the first work package of the ACCORD project analysed the complex landscape of built environment compliance checking and building permitting across Europe to ascertain the requirements for the future digitalisation of this complex interdisciplinary field. The project partners conducted a landscape review and analysis of the current adoption of the concept of digitalisation of building permit processes and compliance checking, including a survey into the attitudes of stakeholders to the prospective digitalisation of this domain in a range of European countries. This work was reported in the D1.1 Landscape Review Report that focused on a) academic projects and methods, b) relevant software tools and technologies, and c) national adoption efforts in the field.

This solid basis paved the way for a framework that has the potential to achieve real change and drive forward the digitalisation of this area.

This work has led to the specification of the ACCORD Semantic Framework that will integrate and provide access to building compliance and permitting services, allowing for the storing, processing, analysis and retrieval of administrative and regulatory information related to construction, renovation and demolition works (documented in Deliverable 1.2). Building on this, a technical specification was developed. This was created by defining the different requirements and usage scenarios and aligning the requirements with the components defined in the ACCORD Framework. This has been formalized into the ACCORD cloud architecture model (documented in Deliverable 4.1). The technical details of the ACCORD cloud services, APIs and Compliance Checking Microservices have been fully elaborated in Deliverable 4.2, and the validation and testing of these have been

documented in Deliverable 4.3.

Evidence of the successful use of these components has been collected through the implementation and demonstration of construction projects in various EU regulatory contexts: the UK, Finland, Estonia, Germany, and Spain. This work is reported in Deliverable 5.1.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

This deliverable has a single aim:

- Produce technical documentation of solutions developed, including the ACCORD Building Compliance Checking Components, Microservices and APIs

It should be noted that the primary content developed as part of this task is not presented in this document, it is what has been delivered as updated to the ACCORD documentation website (<https://docs.accordproject.eu/>), which will stay alive after the ACCORD project ends. This document will summarise the updates added to the documentation website.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is structured into 3 sections. Section 2 will outline the updates made to the ACCORD documentation website, and Section 3 will conclude this deliverable.

2 Additions to the ACCORD Documentation Website

To deliver the technical documentation of this task, the ACCORD Documentation website, originally developed in Task 2.5, was further extended and new content created in Task 4.6.

As a recap, this documentation website is automatically generated from documentation text, written in markdown and stored in the ACCORD Github². An automated build process executes whenever this documentation text is updated to ensure the live version of the website is kept up to date. This approach provides several important advantages:

1. It allows an easy update of documentation text by users who are not web designers/developers.
2. It allows management of versioning of the documentation using standard free tools provided by Github
3. The generated website is hosted for free by Github, ensuring the longevity of the documentation after the end of the ACCORD project.

The key elements of documentation added to the site by this task are:

- **ACCORD Cloud Architecture:** Introduces the ACCORD cloud platform and documents its overall architecture.
- **ACCORD Core Components:** Documents each of the core components of the ACCORD cloud platform.
 - Data Dictionary Repository Component
 - Rule Repository Component
 - Information Requirements Repository
 - IDS Generation Component
 - Model and Data Requirement Validation Component
 - Process Execution Component
 - Data Storage Component
 - Orchestrating Microservices Component
- **ACCORD APIs:** Provides an overview, as well as OpenAPI documentation, for the ACCORD APIs.
- **ACCORD Integration Strategies:** Documents the various methods with which Compliance Checking Microservices can be integrated with the ACCORD Core components.
- **Extensibility of ACCORD Cloud Architecture:** Documents various methods by which future developers can extend the ACCORD architecture.
- **Compliance Checking Microservices:**
 - **Urban Regulations:** Documents the Urban Regulations Microservice used in the Spanish Demonstrator
 - **Solibri and Cloudpermit:** Documents the integration of the Solibri and Cloudpermit systems, as utilised in the Finnish Demonstration.

² Github Repository: <https://github.com/accord-project/accord-documentation>

- **AC(CO2)RD whole life carbon assessment:** Documents the whole life carbon assessment microservice that is used in both the Finnish and Estonian Demonstrator.
- **Clearly.BIM:** Document's the integration of Clearly.BIM that is used in the Estonian Demonstrator.
- **Eurocode Verification:** Documents the Eurocode verification microservice that is used in the UK demonstrator.
- **Land Use Checking:** Documents the Land Use Checking Microservice, as used in the German Demonstrator
- **Environmental Compliance:** Documents the Environmental compliance microservice as used in the German Demonstrator.
- **Timber Construction Compliance Checker:** Documents the timber construction compliance microservice as used in the German Demonstrator.

The documentation website itself can be access at: <https://docs.accordproject.eu/>

3 Conclusions

This deliverable has documented the results of ACCORD's Task 4.6. Specifically, the outputs of the work are the technical documentation of the ACCORD solutions, including the ACCORD Building Compliance Checking Components, Microservices and APIs. This documentation has been deliberately not included directly in this documented, instead it has been integrated into the ACCORD documentation website <https://docs.accordproject.eu/> (building on the work already done in WP2).